

Numerical Solution of Non-Linear Equation in MATLAB

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ABSTRACT: Since Non-linear equations are significant across many disciplines—including physics, engineering, economics, and other sciences—but solving them analytically can be quite challenging. This article explores the application of MATLAB to analyze three numerical methods: False Position, Newton-Raphson, and Secant. Each method is demonstrated through examples implemented in MATLAB, with error graphs provided to assess their accuracy. The study aims to assist in identifying the most appropriate method for solving particular types of nonlinear problems.

KEYWORDS: False Position Method, Newton-Raphson Method, Numerical examples, Secant Method.

INTRODUCTION

A function in one or two variables is said to be non-linear function if the graph does not come to be a straight line or a plane in two dimensions or three dimensions respectively. Consider a function $y = f(x)$, if there is direct change in independent variable x w.r.t dependent variable y , then f is linear. For example $y = 9x + 7$ and, if there is no direct change in independent variable x w.r.t dependent variable y , then f is non-linear function. For example, $y = x^2 + 5$, in science and engineering, there are various problems where relationship between variables is non-linear [1].

Prior to the starting of an iterative procedure, we need to make an initial guess to find either an estimated value of root or an interval in which root lies. One of the simplest methods is to plot the graph of function $f(x)$ and find the interval near the root of interest. Graphical representation also helps us in understanding the properties of function; and hence makes us able to identify the problems in numerical computing.

An iterative procedure ultimately should stop at some stage and we must have some rules for doing this. We may use one of the following tests depending on the behavior of function to stop the process.

1. $|x_{j+1} - x_j| \leq E_a$ (Absolute error in x)
2. $\left| \frac{x_{j+1} - x_j}{x_{j+1}} \right| \leq E_r$ (Relative error in x), $x \neq 0$
3. $|f(x_{j+1}) - f(x_j)| \leq E$ (Difference in function value)
4. $|f(x)| \leq F_{max}$ (Large function value)
5. $|x_j| \leq XL$ (Large value of x)

Here, x_j represent estimate of root at its iteration and $f(x_j)$ is values of function of x_j these are situation where those tests fail when used alone or sometimes-in combination. A practical convergence test should always use a combination of these tests. If in case, we do not know whether a test converges or not, we must have a limit on number of iterations, like iteration $\geq N$ (limit of iteration) [1, 2].

Let $f(x) = 0$ be any equation and ξ be any root of $f(x) = 0$. Let $\{x_j\}$ the denotes the sequence of successive iteration for ξ , then error in j th iteration is $e_j = \xi - x_j$, then an approximation of e_j say h_j can be define as $h_j = x_{j+1} - x_j = e_j - e_{j+1}$, if $e_j \rightarrow 0$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$, then iteration procedure converges [3].

Consider $\{b_j\}_{j=0}^{\infty}$, such that $b_j \rightarrow b$ as $j \rightarrow \infty$, with $b_j \neq b$ for every j . If for $\lambda, \beta > 0$, then $\lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \frac{|b_{j+1} - b|}{|b_j - b|^\beta} = \lambda$, then $\{b_j\}_{j=0}^{\infty}$ converges to b with order β and λ is an asymptotic error constant. The order of iterative technique of the form $b_j = g(b_{j-1})$ is β , if the sequence $\{b_j\}_{j=0}^{\infty}$ converges to the solution $b = g(b)$ of order β . Usually, higher order of convergence sequence converges

more swiftly than with a lower order sequence. The speed of convergence affected by the asymptotic constant but degree of the order remains unaffected. If $\beta = 1$ (and $\lambda < 1$), the sequence is linearly convergent and is called quadratically convergent for $\beta = 2$ [4]. The following methods exemplify MATLAB accurate calculation of roots.

Algorithm for the Method of False Position

Step 1: begin the program.

Step 2: denote the function by $f(x)$.

Step 3: take two variables x_0 and x_1 .

Step 4: check $f(x_0) * f(x_1) < 0$. if, yes then repeat the step (5 and 9).

Step 5: find $x_2 = \frac{x_0 f(x_1) - x_1 f(x_0)}{f(x_1) - f(x_0)}$

Step 6: If $f(x_0) * f(x_2) < 0$, then write $x_1 = x_2$, if $f(x_0) * f(x_2) > 0$ set $x_0 = x_2$.

Step 7: if $|x_0 - x_1| < e$, e being the recommended precision, then repeat the step 8 else 5.

Step 8: print the approximate answer.

Step 9: end the program [3, 5, 2].

MATLAB Code for Method of False Position

MATLAB code for method of false position is given below:

```
function [x error]=falseposition1(f,xl,xu,err)
% It will take function and initial value as the input of %function.
% You would require to run it in command window as
% falseposition (@(x)(x^3-2*x-5),2,3,0.1^10)
% where x^2 + 2*x -5 is function, [2,3] initial values and %0.1^10 is maximum error tolerable and plot the error.
display('Solution of Given equation by Regula falsi Method')
i=1;
while(i)
    if f(xl)*f(xu)<0
        i=0;
    else
        warning('Enter proper range');
        xl=input('Enter lower value:');
        xu=input('Enter upper value: ');
    end
end
if f(xl)<0
    xn=xl;
    xp=xu;
else
    xn=xu;
    xp=xl;
end
iter=1;
x=(xn*f(xp)-xp*f(xn))/(f(xp)-f(xn));
xx=x;
disp('Iteration    xn          f(xn)          xp          f(xp)          x          f(x)');
while (abs(f(x))>err)
    x=(xn*f(xp)-xp*f(xn))/(f(xp)-f(xn));
```



```
error(iter)=f(x)-f(xx);
if f(x)<0
    xn=x;
else
    xp=x;
end
disp(num2str([iter xn f(xn) xp f(xp) x f(x)], '%20.10f'));
xx=x;
iter=iter+1;
end
display(['Root is x = ' num2str(x)]);
plot(error)
xlabel('Number of iterations')
ylabel('Error')
end
```

Algorithm for the Newton-Raphson Method

- Step 1: begin the program.
- Step 2: denote the function by $f(x), f'(x)$.
- Step 3: take the initial approximation of the zero x_0 and take $j = 0$.
- Step 5: find $x_{j+1} = x_j - [f(x_j)/f'(x_j)]$.
- Step 1: if $|x_{j+1} - x_j| < e$, e being the prescribed precision then repeat step 7.
- Step 6: take $j = j + 1$ and repeat Step 4.
- Step 7: print the approximate answer.
- Step 8: end the program [3, 5].

MATLAB Code for Newton-Raphson Method

```
% The Newton Raphson method, inter the function f=x^3-2*x-5
% here and you would require to run it in command window as
% inter the approximate root:3
% inter the accuracy: 0.0000000001
syms x
f=1/x-sin(x)+1;
fdash=diff(f);
disp('The equation is: '),disp(f);
disp('The derivative of equation is: '),disp(fdash);
y=inline(f);
dy=inline(fdash);
x0=input('Enter approximate root: ');
e=input('Enter the accuracy: ');
disp('Iteration    x0        f(x0)        df(x0)');
x1=x0;
iter = 1;
disp(num2str([iter x0 feval(y,x0) feval(dy,x0)], '%15.10f'));
while abs(feval(y,x0))>e
    x1=x0;
```



```
h=-feval(y,x0)/feval(dy,x0);
x0=x0+h;
x2=x0;
disp(num2str([iter x0 feval(y,x0) feval(dy,x0)],'%15.10f'));
error(iter)=feval(y,x2)-feval(y,x1);
iter=iter+1;
end
plot(error)
xlabel('Number of iterations')
```

Algorithm of Secant Method

Step 1: begin the program.

Step 2: denote the function by $f(x)$.

Step 3: take the initial approximation of the zero x_0 and x_1 .

Step 5: find $x_{j+1} = x_j - [(x_j - x_{j-1})/(f(x_j) - f(x_{j-1}))]f(x_j)$

Step 1: if $|x_j - x_{j-1}| < e$, e being the recommended precision then repeat step 7 and 6.

Step 6: take $x_j = x_{j-1}$, $x_j = x_{j+1}$ and repeat Step 4.

Step 7: print the approximate answer.

Step 8: end the program [3,5, 2].

MATLAB Code for Secant Method

```
function secant(f,xn_1,xn_2,maxerr,maxiter)
% It will take function and initial value as the input of %function.
% You would require to run it in command window as
% secant (@(x)(x^3 -2*x -5),2,3.5,0.1^10)
% where x^3 -2*x-5 is function,[2,3]initial values and %0.0000000001 is maximum error tolerable and plot the error.
disp('Solution by Secant Method')
xn = (xn_1*f(xn_2) - xn_2*f(xn_1))/(f(xn_2) - f(xn_1));
disp('Iteration      xn_1      f(xn_1)      xn_2      f(xn_1)      xn      f(xn)');
flag = 1;
xn1=xn;
disp(num2str([flag xn_1 f(xn_1) xn_2 f(xn_2) xn f(xn)],'%20.10f'));
while abs((xn-xn_2)/xn) > maxerr && flag <= maxiter
    xn_2 = xn_1;
    xn_1 = xn;
    xn = (xn_1*f(xn_2) - xn_2*f(xn_1))/(f(xn_2) - f(xn_1));
    error(flag)=f(xn)-f(xn1);
    flag = flag + 1;
    disp(num2str([flag xn_1 f(xn_1) xn_2 f(xn_2) xn f(xn)],'%20.10f'));
    if(flag == maxiter)
        break;
    end
    xn1=xn;
end
if flag < maxiter
    display(['Root is x = ' num2str(xn)]);
```



```
else
    display('Root does not exist');
end
plot(error)
xlabel('Number of iterations')
ylabel('Error')
```

Numerical Experiment

In this part we are going to take the numerical examples and see the number of iteration that is needed for the given precision. We will apply in $e = 0.1^{10}$. We use MATLAB software version R2010a.

Example 1. [6,7] We solve $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ applies Regula-falsi method, in the interval [-1.3,-0.5].

```
>> falseposition(@(x) 1/x-sin(x)+1,-1.3,-0.5,0.0000000001);
```

Solution of given equation by Regula falsi Method

Table 1. Regula-Falsi Method $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$

Iteration	xn	$f(xn)$	xp	$f(xp)$	x	$f(x)$
1.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.7428474623	0.3302165479	-0.7428474623	0.3302165479
2.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6485913527	0.0622615482	-0.6485913527	0.0622615482
3.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6327180581	0.0108560574	-0.6327180581	0.0108560574
4.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6300068949	0.0018661136	-0.6300068949	0.0018661136
5.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6295425213	0.0003199863	-0.6295425213	0.0003199863
6.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294629431	0.0000548454	-0.6294629431	0.0000548454
7.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294493049	0.0000093998	-0.6294493049	0.0000093998
8.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294469675	0.0000016110	-0.6294469675	0.0000016110
9.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294465669	0.0000002761	-0.6294465669	0.0000002761
10.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294464983	0.0000000473	-0.6294464983	0.0000000473
11.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294464865	0.0000000081	-0.6294464865	0.0000000081
12.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294464845	0.0000000014	-0.6294464845	0.0000000014
13.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294464841	0.0000000002	-0.6294464841	0.0000000002
14.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.6294464841	0.0000000000	-0.6294464841	0.0000000000

Following graph shows plot of error of the equation of $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ by method of false position:

Fig. 1: Plot of Error by Method of False Position

Example 2. we solve $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ applies Newton-Raphson method and $x_0 = -0.5$, in the interval $[-1.3, -0.5]$.

The equation is:

$$1/x - \sin(x) + 1$$

The derivative of equation is:

$$-\cos(x) - 1/x^2$$

Enter approximate root: -0.5

Enter the accuracy: 0.0000000001

Table 2: Newton-Raphson $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$

Iteration	x_0	$f(x_0)$	$df(x_0)$
1.0000000000	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-4.8775825619
1.0000000000	-0.6067279651	-0.0780026321	-3.5380322375
2.0000000000	-0.6287748620	-0.0022399982	-3.3381029345
3.0000000000	-0.6294459013	-0.0000019419	-3.3323179677
4.0000000000	-0.6294464841	-0.0000000000	-3.3323129512

Following graph shows plot of error of the equation of $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ by Newton-Raphson method.

Fig. 2: Plot of Error by Newton-Raphson Method

Example 3. We solve $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ applies Secant method, in the interval $[-1.3, -0.5]$.

Now we enter these commands.

```
>> secant(@(x) 1/x-sin(x)+1,-1.3,-0.5,0.0000000001,20);
```

Solution by Secant Method

Table 3. Secant Method $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$

Iteration	x_{n-1}	$f(x_{n-1})$	x_{n-2}	$f(x_{n-2})$	x_n	$f(x_n)$
1.0000000000	-1.3000000000	1.1943274162	-0.5000000000	-0.5205744614	-0.7428474623	0.3302165479
2.0000000000	-0.7428474623	0.3302165479	-1.3000000000	1.1943274162	-0.5299338255	-0.3815518183
3.0000000000	-0.5299338255	-0.3815518183	-0.7428474623	0.3302165479	-0.6440686889	0.0478245396
4.0000000000	-0.6440686889	0.0478245396	-0.5299338255	-0.3815518183	-0.6313561881	0.0063480777

5.0000000000	-0.6313561881	0.0063480777	-0.6440686889	0.0478245396	-0.6294105076	-0.0001198904
6.0000000000	-0.6294105076	-0.0001198904	-0.6313561881	0.0063480777	-0.6294465728	0.0000002956
7.0000000000	-0.6294465728	0.0000002956	-0.6294105076	-0.0001198904	-0.6294464841	0.0000000000
8.0000000000	-0.6294464841	0.0000000000	-0.6294465728	0.0000002956	-0.6294464841	-0.0000000000
9.0000000000	-0.6294464841	-0.0000000000	-0.6294464841	0.0000000000	-0.6294464841	-0.0000000000

Following graph shows plot of error of the equation of $f(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \sin(x) + 1 = 0$ by Secant method

Fig. 3: Plot of Error by Secant Method

CONCLUSION

The results indicate that MATLAB possesses robust computational capabilities, making it highly effective for finding the roots of nonlinear equations using numerical methods. In this study, we examined several iterative methods for root finding of nonlinear equations. Each method was applied to a specific problem, and the corresponding error graphs for each method were plotted.

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